

**ABOUT THE ROLE OF CORRECT ESTABLISHMENT OF THE TEACHER-STUDENT
RELATIONSHIP IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS**

Hajiyeva F.

Nakhchivan State University, head teacher

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Abstract

In the presented research work, the work done in the general education schools located in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, the reforms carried out, the mutual communication between students and teachers, their joint activities, the development of creative thinking in them by using individual approach in the training process and research methods were discussed. Also, the goals set by the teacher in the training process, the organization of training using the principle of systematicity and consistency, the positive role of parents in maintaining regular relations in training, and the process of creating enthusiasm for the lesson in students using humor were explained in detail.

As a result, we can note that the effect of complex reforms in education is ultimately realized in the classroom environment and serves to improve the learning results of students. Correct establishment of "teacher-student" relationship in schools, revealing their knowledge, skills and habits by approaching students individually, identifying their abilities and directing them in that direction helps students to form and develop properly.

Keywords: teacher, student, innovations, goals, education, teaching, order, discipline

The long and rich historical experience of mankind proves that education and science form the basis of public and social progress. Our great leader, Heydar Aliyev, who created the foundations of Azerbaijan's statehood, saw the only way to the progress of our people in education, science and culture, and dedicated his life and activities to the realization of this goal. Our great leader considered science and education to be the most powerful means of development.

The great leader Heydar Aliyev, who deeply knows that education is an important area of every society and state, noted that the future of the people of Azerbaijan, independent Azerbaijan, depends on the knowledge, education and upbringing that young people receive today. These will preserve the moral values of our people and the independence of our country.

Heydar Aliyev recommended learning to protect the high national and moral values of our people formed over many centuries and passing them on to future generations. Therefore, the teacher's activity also includes evaluating the student's knowledge, skills and habits, and finding the reasons for their achievements and setbacks. The teacher should know the class he/she teaches very well, the learning-teaching process should be suitable for the subject, the class and the teacher, it is necessary to measure the level of learning at the end of the education and to have a multi-directional orientation of all activities. Measurement and evaluation activity has an important function in carrying out all these works.

By the decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated February 25, 2008, No.714, "The best teacher competition" was approved. The main goal of the competition is to reveal the potential of creative teachers working in the country's general education institutions, to identify talented teachers who are distinguished by their successful results in the field of applying modern learning technologies, to create effective conditions for innovative teachers to demonstrate their

pedagogical skills, to raise the status and reputation of the teacher in society, to achieve a gradual increase in the role of the teacher in the implementation of the educational policy and to bring to the attention of the general public that stimulating measures are important in raising their level of professionalism. A good teacher means a good student. The more educated and professional the teacher is, the more educated and talented our students are.

Day by day increasing achievement in Azerbaijani schools is obvious. A good teacher-student relationship means a highly talented and high-level student. Our successes continue and our achievements increase (Sulaymanova A., "Basics of education", 2014, p. 58).

The organization and implementation of electronic education at a high level in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic is one of the most obvious examples of adaptation to modern requirements. When determining the main directions of the development of the education of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, information and communication technologies were brought to the fore in secondary schools, since 2005, information and communication technologies (ICT) have been applied in the education system, which has made both our teachers' and students' work even easier.

Special trainings on information and communication technologies have been conducted since 2003. The "Electronic school" project has been started in 50 educational institutions of our republic, and the existing DATA center, electronic educational resources database, and unified educational portal have started to provide effective management. It stimulates better understanding between teachers and students and leads to mastering the lesson, gaining high achievements, effective management, and achieving high success (Sulaymanova A., "Basics of education", 2014, p. 58).

After our country gained independence, important tasks were set in all areas, as well as in education. The problems of changing and updating the education system have been put forward, the issues of integration

into the education system of leading countries such as the USA, Europe, etc. have been brought to the fore. Great leader Heydar Aliyev said: "the main goal of reforming the education system now is to ensure that the Azerbaijani education system adapts to the standards of the world education system". In the "State Strategy for the Development of Education in the Republic of Azerbaijan", the directions of development of the education system that meet the state education standards and the goals in accordance with modern requirements have been defined, and new responsible tasks have been set for the education workers. (State Strategy for the Development of Education in the Republic of Azerbaijan, 2013, p. 105)

The education system in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic also improves its education using the principles of education of the most advanced countries, carries out content and structural changes, issues of preparing curricula at all levels of education are considered. All schools of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic have been renovated and the education system has developed at a very high speed.

In general, modern technologies are used in all schools of our republic.

Teaching is a universal occupation. Everyone teaches each other something. In order for the learning process to be effective, it is important to establish a special relationship between the teacher and the learner. A good teacher should have whatever qualities make him good.

If such characteristics as mutually active listening, respect and trust, joint problem solving, sharing their own opinions are formed between the teacher and the student, then the teacher-student relationship is purposefully established.

Sometimes, during training, teachers give students such messages that irritate the student. For example, warning students, teaching a moral lesson, intimidating, etc. threats annoy the student. The teacher thinks he is helping the student by doing these things. However, at this time, it affects the student's personality, and he resents the teacher, the lesson, and the school. (State Strategy for the Development of Education in the Republic of Azerbaijan, 2013, p. 105)

Sometimes criticizing the student or praising him inappropriately also irritates the student. The main goal of the teacher is to provide quality education to the student. (Scientific-methodical "Curricula" magazine, No. 2016, p. 23).

Almost every school has the following categories of teachers:

- creative teachers;
- teachers with pedagogical diligence;
- teachers who require special attention.

Creative teachers follow state standards, enhance their personal learning, use different forms of presentation for each lesson, and more. They have clearly defined goals.

In the world of education, the goals that a teacher sets for a student are to achieve their goals. Success and the organization of a goal-oriented training process depend on well-prepared planning in advance.

Teachers with pedagogical diligence try to follow the state standards, are eager to learn, follow the rules correctly, and can develop any skills in students. Working on themselves, they will become creative teachers in the future (State Strategy for the Development of Education in the Republic of Azerbaijan, 2013, p. 93). And teachers who require special attention are those who do not meet modern requirements. They are indifferent to the subjects taught, innovations, state standards. It is necessary to involve such teachers in seminars, trainings, and to keep their personal education in focus.

Teaching is a special profession that undertakes the task of education, teaching and related management of the state. Teachers are constantly faced with different student potentials. These differences may appear in the form of age groups, subject areas at potential levels, and socio-economic structure. In such cases, it requires teachers to use different approaches, methods and techniques.

The teacher is the first and fundamental level among those who manage education. The quality of educational management is related to the quality of the teacher's classroom management. Classroom management can be grouped into reactive, precautionary, developmental and holistic models.

Democracy is important in using the reactive model. While using the responsive model in order to change the behavior of a student who does not bring books and notebooks to class, methods such as meeting with the student, meeting with parents, and socializing are used. The use and forms of these methods are implemented with different options. Reactive model is also called classical model. (Mehrabov. A., Development technology of personality-oriented educational standards, Azerbaijan school, 2005, p. 71)

A precautionary model is a planned model. According to this model, an action plan should be developed in advance for undesirable outcomes and behaviors. This model socializes classroom activities and systematizes misbehavior.

The developmental model is based on the realization of physical and cognitive development levels of students in classroom management. In order to manage the class with this model, it is necessary to form these skills in the students first.

The rules of conduct to be chosen during the listed measures should be consistent with the student's developmental stages. Models are a system of classroom management, which includes the activities of students at school, family, and leisure time. Classroom management is multi-directional and requires a lot of effort. It is necessary to be with students during the day, to plan their behavior, to be aware of everything in the class. The teacher should regularly deal with the students. Unfortunately, some teachers do not realize this (New state programs (curricula) at the general education level, 2013, p.92).

The most important key to classroom management is love and mutual respect. In such an environment there will be positive discipline. We must not forget that without mutual love, the process of education cannot give good results. First, students should be made to

love the school and the class, and then they should move on to teaching.

Sometimes teachers in schools make decisions on their own. But every decision should be discussed together with the students. In a class where there are common denominator decisions, following them does not escape the attention of the students before the teacher. This is also important in class management. Of course, the teacher also has decisions that are particularly necessary. In general, the main goal of our state is quality education. The goal of all reforms in the field of education is to improve its quality.

Since the student's learning results appear as the final result of all the activities that take place in the field of education, it is possible to evaluate the teaching activity of the teacher, the educational institutions, and the educational system of the country as a whole. An assessment system is being created in the general education system of the Republic of Azerbaijan. (Mammadova Y., Development history of general education schools in Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, 2022, p. 72)

The teacher's activity also includes evaluating the student's knowledge, skills and habits, and finding the reasons for their achievements and struggles. The teacher should know the class he teaches very well (State Strategy for the Development of Education in the Republic of Azerbaijan, 2015, p. 28).

A student spends most of his time at school with his teacher and classmates. The teacher-student relationship is very different from other relationships because it is about learning and teaching.

Words and contact form the basis of teacher-student relationship. The ability of the teacher to establish a good dialogue with the student ensures the student's more active participation in the lesson. A student who can communicate with his teacher comfortably and without hesitation can actively perform the tasks assigned to him and have a good effect on everyone with his exemplary behavior. While teaching, the teacher must constantly think about how to establish a dialogue with his students and how to guide them.

Students are very quickly influenced by teachers. In order to have a good education, student-teacher relations must be at a very high level. A teacher should always be loved by a student.

A good teacher should have specific goals. He should know that he is on the right path and have the right goal.

A good teacher should be able to work without expecting anything in return. During a school day, the main task of a teacher should be to be very sincere with the students, to say that the lesson went very well and to end the lesson with a smile. In general, the teacher should be able to evaluate the student's ideas.

It is very important to know how students feel about the lesson. A teacher who does not listen to his students will soon be known as an incompetent teacher. However, a teacher who listens to his students all day long, answers their questions in detail and honestly, and fully fulfills the students' ideas is recognized and respected by the students as a competent teacher

(Mammadova Y., Development history of general education schools in Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, 2022, p. 55).

A teacher should also have exemplary behavior. Good teachers should have a pleasant and happy appearance, full of life energy. Positive thinking will contribute to the development of creative abilities. A teacher must believe that every student will succeed. Students want to see smart and educated people around them who will see their skills. Skilled teachers always set high goals for students, explain that it is normal to make mistakes on the way to success, and create conditions. This will give students a good motivation so that they do not lose heart even if they make mistakes on the way to the goal (Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan on education, "Curricula" magazine, No. 2009, p.57).

A good teacher should also have a sense of humor, say sincere words, and be able to take risks.

Taking risks is part of the formula for success. When students make mistakes while taking risks, they will watch with great interest and attention as you show them how to overcome those mistakes. This is very important and valuable (State Strategy for the Development of Education in the Republic of Azerbaijan, 2015, p. 109).

Teachers should be able to do their work consistently, and they should always be in touch with parents. Communication between parents and teachers is very important and valuable for a student to be competent. It is necessary to establish a relationship with parents so that they can easily turn to the teacher if they have any concerns. If the relationship between parents and teacher is good, then the student's choice will be right (Scientific-methodical "Curricula" magazine, No. 2016, p. 125).

A teacher should enjoy his work and be adaptable to the needs of students. As students grow, teaching methods must also change. A connection must be made between the students and the goals. In this case, there will be fewer problems (Məmmədova Y., History of the development of secondary schools in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, 2022, P. 56).

In general, the teacher should welcome changes in the classroom. Sometimes changing the classroom also gives new motivation to the students and sometimes changing the desks, changing the students' place changes the mood of the class. This helps the students to participate enthusiastically in class with renewed energy.

The teacher should always provide emotional support to the students and sometimes bring fun to the class. You can't be overly serious in the classroom. On some days, the goal should be "entertainment". A competent teacher should be constantly interested in the psychological states of children. Depression, anxiety, and mental stress can seriously affect learning time.

The teacher should never stop learning, sometimes he should also be able to change his own strict rules. These rules can sometimes be personal rules. For example, someone who says "I will never do this" or a teacher who says "I will never allow students to grade each other" can set a strict rule for himself. The teacher should know that the effect of changing the rules for the

students will be good (Scientific-methodical "Curricula" magazine, No. 2016, p. 85).

Finally, the teacher should be a professional in his field. In addition to the educational methodology, he should know his field well, never stop learning, and be in search of interest (Zakharova I.G., (2003) Information technologies in education, p. 159).

Therefore, our highly educated students study in all schools of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. Every year, the number of students admitted to universities is increasing, and this is due to the joint efforts of both our teachers and parents. We know that the teacher-student relationship is at a very high level, and we will try to continue it.

Research method: In the study formed in the scanning model, the information obtained by referring to the scientific literature related to the topic was summarized. At the same time, observations were made in various schools of Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, negative and positive cases of student-teacher relations were discussed and the obtained examples were explained in detail.

Experimental findings: In the years of independence, secondary schools in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic have successfully developed. Education in all secondary schools of Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic has achieved great achievements organically connected with the enlightenment movement. In the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, since the beginning of the 20th century, the educational network has been expanded, a new generation of enlightened intellectuals has been born, and the activities of secular schools have begun. One of the most important changes in education during this period was the involvement of Azerbaijani girls in education. Since the main paradigms in the pedagogical approach have changed in modern times, the teacher-student relationship should also be adjusted accordingly. The student's development from an object to a subject, treating him as a person, requires the entire educational process to be based on the student's interests and abilities, and to take into account his individual psychological characteristics. Today, a completely different person is standing in front of the teacher, who was silent in class, answered only when asked a question, and did not show any initiative. Now the student cooperates with the teacher, freely expresses his thoughts and opinions, gives an opinion, can show a different approach, and can even agree with the teacher on certain issues.

Conclusion and suggestions: New educational concepts are being applied in the countries of the world. For a year now, new educational programs have been implemented in the schools of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic and of course, teachers play a crucial role in changes in the reform process. The effect of complex reforms in education is ultimately realized in the classroom environment and serves to improve the learning results of students. Many things are done in schools to improve the teacher-student relationship. The analysis of the two most important documents,

which conceptually justify the development of education and its implementation in Azerbaijan - "General Education Concept of the Republic of Azerbaijan" National Curriculum (2006) and "State Standards and Program Curricula of the General Education Level" (2011) once again confirms that in schools the pedagogical process should meet the needs of the student's formation as a whole personality, meet the educational expectations of the society, and fulfill the goals and tasks set by the state at the appropriate level. The newly approved concept of education is significantly different from 20-30 years ago. Development of education in Azerbaijan also depends on the correct establishment of teacher-student relations. It should be noted that long-term studies show that the development of students in various schools of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic is the result of the systematic and correct attitude of teachers. This relationship also allows students to freely express their opinions and learn to apply the materials they have mastered in classes with new curricula. This leads to strengthening of knowledge and success in them. In addition, teachers connect students' academic skills with social skills (Süleymanova A., "Basics of Education", 2014, p. 152).

Classroom research suggests that the level of support provided by teachers at the initial stage of curriculum reform, confidence in their professional levels, and long-term experiences lead to better student motivation and better reading ((Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan on Education, "Curricula" magazine, No. 2009, p. 92).

Based on the results obtained from the research, it can be concluded that the systematic work of the "teacher-student" union in schools, approaching students individually and revealing their knowledge, skills and habits, determining their abilities and directing them in that direction helps students to form and develop properly.

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